

iJERResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, March- 2023 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10104855

THE CHALLENGES OF VACCINATION IN THE STATE OF AMAZONAS

AUTHORS

Josy Lira Dias (joliradias@gmail.com), Valeska Regina Soares Marques (valeska_br@hotmail.com)

ABSTRACT

The population of the interior of the state of Amazonas lacks basic health care and actions such as vaccination. Given this problem, what are the main challenges to be overcome in relation to vaccination in the state of Amazonas?